

IMPROVING INVENTORY ACCOUNTING AND INTERNAL AUDIT IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the main issues of documenting the movement of goods and material reserves in budget organizations were considered, the list of initial accounting documents, accounting registers were determined. Methodological aspects of documenting the movement of goods and material reserves in budget organizations are revealed. The practical aspects of documenting the movement of goods and materials are considered based on legal documents.

Commodity and material reserves are an important factor in ensuring the activities of budget organizations, requiring prompt, complete information about their existence and movement in order to determine real needs. Since accounting involves documenting all economic processes of the organization's economic activity, the issues of documenting such an asset element as commodity and material reserves are very relevant. In budget organizations, each economic transaction carried out with commodity and material reserves is documented. That is, this can be exemplified by the cases of receipt and expenditure of commodity and material reserves in organizations, their transfer from one place to another, and the change of materially responsible persons. The purpose of documenting the movement of commodity and material reserves in budget organizations is to ensure the correct reflection of commodity and material reserves in the organization in the forms of internal control and financial reporting [7].

Since the accuracy and reliability of accounting and financial reporting data is confirmed by a mandatory inventory of assets and liabilities, it is also necessary to fully document the movement of inventory in budget organizations. Because during the inventory process, along with inventory, their documents are also fully checked. Therefore, the employees of the accounting service of budget organizations and financially responsible persons must fully and correctly reflect the movement of inventory in accounting documents, both from a legal and methodological point of view. This also determines the relevance of the selected research topic.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Within the framework of the research topic, the scientific works of domestic and foreign economists were studied. The practical aspects of the research conducted by scientists were also analyzed.

In the works of foreign economists I.P. Vorobyeva, A.L. Spesivtseva and G.A. Barysheva, material reserves are defined as "part of the non-financial assets of a state institution necessary for the performance of its social, managerial and other functions in accordance with

its charter." Scientists have classified material reserves and scientifically and methodologically substantiated that the most important task of accounting policy in budgetary organizations is to ensure the preservation and targeted use of material reserves. Also, the primary documents and registers that serve as the basis for accounting for material reserves are reflected in a table [4].

The procedure for recognizing material reserves, the methodology for their classification, valuation, and documentation of business transactions on their movement were reflected in the scientific research of OE Kachkova, TI Kryshaleva, and MF Ovsyichuk.

The methods of receiving and writing off material reserves in budget organizations, their composition, classification by groups and types of accounts, and the formation of their actual cost according to the purchase method have also been covered in detail by scholars [5].

Among the economists of our country, M. Astanakulov studied the scientific and practical aspects of accounting for material reserves in budget organizations. The composition of material reserves, their reflection in accounting sub-accounts, analytical and synthetic accounting and documentation are briefly described.

The issues of organizing inventory accounting in budget organizations, its purpose and features, accounting for income and their assessment, write-offs, organizing analytical and synthetic accounting for inventory, and using information systems in inventory accounting were considered in the studies of A.J. Tuychiev, A.A. Ostonokulov, K.Sh. Ibragimov, and A.S. Tursunov. The indicators established to determine the established norm of inventory are also scientifically and methodologically substantiated by scientists, illustrated with practical examples.

When we familiarized ourselves with the research conducted by the above economists within the framework of this topic, we found that their works mainly covered the accounting of commodity and material reserves in budget organizations, and partially indicated the accounting documents used in accounting for commodity and material reserves. However, no separate research was conducted on the issues of documenting the movement of commodity and material reserves in budget organizations. For this reason, we consider it necessary to conduct research within the framework of this topic.

Systematic analysis, analysis, synthesis, comparison and other similar research methods were used in budgetary organizations to improve the methodological aspects of documenting the movement of goods and materials, taking into account the rules of budget accounting.

In addition, in accordance with the approved work plan of the Internal Audit Service Department for 2024, 62 audit objects were selected for 12 audit activities, of which 6 audit activities were conducted in 33 audit objects in the first half of the year. Based on the circumstances identified during the audit activities, suggestions and recommendations were given to the heads of audit objects to eliminate errors and shortcomings in the appropriate manner.

The internal audit service department is constantly providing proposals and recommendations and practical assistance to employees in the system on the correct management of the indicators of salaries and equivalent payments, public procurement, debtor and creditor debts, inventory accounting, financial reports.

The list of control objects that can be selected by citizens is being included in the "State Audit" program by the first day of the first month of each quarter for the implementation of audit activities with the participation of citizens. For the 3rd quarter, audit activities will be carried out at 2 audit facilities selected by citizens. Official reports on the results of audit activities conducted by the internal audit service are included in the "State Audit" program.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Inventories include assets with a useful life of no more than one year or used within one operating cycle. Inventories include goods and other assets purchased by budget organizations or intended for resale.

The above figure shows the types of commodity and material reserves, and each commodity and material reserve is recorded in accounting based on primary accounting documents. In budget organizations, the receipt, transfer, change of materially responsible persons and write-off of commodity and material reserves are fully documented with primary accounting documents. We can also see this in the documentation process by types of commodity and material reserve movements in budget organizations (Table 1)

Primary accounting documents for recording types of movements of inventory

Table 1

Document name	Goods - types of material reserves	Who formalizes	Comments
Waybill	All goods - material reserves	Goods suppliers	Includes: goods - transport waybill and transport waybill
Invoice			The consignment note and invoice are also included
Certificate		Materially responsible person and representative of the goods supplier (with the participation of the commission formed by the organization)	Documents are drawn up in the following cases: in cases of inconsistency between the actual existence of documents and their information, during the liquidation of fixed assets, during the inspection and acceptance of the quality of goods and material reserves.
Application - bill of lading (Bill of lading (Application))	Goods are material resources, recorded at their actual cost formed during their purchase, production, and conversion into finished products.	The material responsible person of the unit that transfers material valuables	The form of the document and its application are approved by the Instruction "On Accounting in Budgetary Institutions" (December 22, 2010, No. 2169).
Accounting certificate	All goods - material reserves	Accounting	The form of the document and its application are approved by the Instruction "On Accounting in Budgetary Institutions" (December 22, 2010, No. 2169).
Moving inventory from place to place (or change of financially responsible persons)			
Waybill (Request)	All goods - material reserves	The material responsible person of the unit that supplies material	The form of documents and their application are approved by the Instruction "On Accounting in Budgetary
Menu-Request for	Food products		

Record of feed and fodder supplied	Feed and fodder for livestock and other animals	Accounting	Organizations" (December 22, 2010, No. 2169).
List of materials provided for the needs of the organization	All goods - material reserves		
Fence map	All goods - material reserves		
Certificate	All goods - material reserves		
serving food products		valuables	

The data in the table above shows that in budget organizations, each primary accounting document that records the types of movements of goods and material reserves is necessarily drawn up by materially responsible persons or accounting service employees in accordance with current regulatory legal acts [6].

If the budget organization independently develops the forms of primary accounting documents, their list should be approved by the organization's accounting policy or by order of the head. This is an acceptable solution for accounting for business processes for which standard forms are not provided.

Inventory in budget organizations is divided into the following types (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Types of inventory in budget organizations.

In accounting, the synthetic account of operations on goods - material reserves is reflected based on the information of the relevant memorial orders, the organization's General Journal Book (form No. 308) and financial reporting forms.

Nowadays, since the accounting of budget organizations is completely conducted electronically in the "UzASBO" software package, accounting work has become much easier, and the documentation of the movements of commodity and material reserves and their control have become somewhat faster [7].

At the same time, budget organizations must adhere to the requirements and norms of current regulatory legal acts when documenting the movement of goods and material resources.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that the movement of commodity and material reserves in budget organizations should be regulated by the "Organizational Document Circulation Schedule", which allows for the optimization of documentation work and control. This schedule fully indicates the name of the documents, the time of preparation, verification, processing and submission of the document to the archive, and the responsible person. Also, the deadlines for submitting reports on commodity and material reserves and materially responsible persons are indicated in the section of departments and divisions of the budget organization. This allows for the timely receipt of information on commodity and material reserves.

The "Organizational Document Flow Chart" is included as an appendix to the organization's accounting policy or can be approved by a separate management order. A properly developed "Organizational Document Flow Chart" ensures the quality of the accounting service's work with the organization's departments and divisions, the timely submission of reports by accountants and responsible persons, and the implementation of internal control. This has a positive effect on the financial and economic activities of budget organizations.

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